

SOLID-LIQUID PRESSURE BONDING FOR FABRICATING STEEL/ALUMINUM ALLOY LAMINATED COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The interface structures and bond properties of steel/Al-20Sn-1Cu system was studied by solid-liquid pressure bonding for commercial fabrication of laminated composites in industry. The effects of processing parameters on bond properties were investigated based on various bonding procedures and shear strength tests. The results showed that the optimum preheating temperature of the liquid alloy is 790 °C and that an applied pressure can increase the bonding efficiency greatly. The intermetallic layers have been found to form in the temperature range of 730°C to 820°C. Intermetallic compounds Fe_2Al_3 and FeAl_3 were identified in these layers. Another factor degrading bond properties is the segregation of tin at the interfaces. The addition of rare-earth elements to the liquid alloys can improve the uniformity of aluminum alloy and resist the intermetallic compound development as well as the diffusion process.

KEYWORDS: laminate, diffusion, pressure bonding, two-phase processing, aluminum alloy/steel couple, interface property, intermetallic compound, processing parameter

INTRODUCTION

Classical laminate plate theory and manufacturing techniques have been successfully developed to improve the strength, toughness and thermal shock resistance in laminated metal matrix composites. Two typical processing routes, solid phase processes (e.g., plate rolling) and two phase processing methods (e.g., consolidation casting), are currently being employed to fabricate laminated composites. However, their widespread acceptance is hindered by a lack of production efficiency and high material cost. Experiences acquired over the past several years have shown clearly the need to focus equally on affordability and scientific issues. So a potential processing technology combining rolling with casting offers commercial advantages over conventional techniques by pressure bonding liquid metal to solid sheet using industrial rolling system. Successful fabrication of laminated composites through this method requires accurate

knowledge of the bonding parameters, interfacial structures, and chemical reaction process [1-3].

Previous research was mainly concerned with the formation and growth mechanisms of interfacial products in Fe-Al system and effort was often directed towards adherence [4-6], but only limited information has been obtained based on the two-phase pressure bonding of steel and aluminum alloys system in spite of its extensive technological applications. The purpose of this work is to develop a steel/aluminum alloy pressure bonding system by determining the effects of processing parameters on bonding properties and investigating interface microstructures.

EXPERIMENT

A commercial carbide steel containing 0.068% C, 0.02% Si, 0.009% P, 0.3% Mn, 0.017% S, 0.067% Al, and balance. Fe was used for this investigation in terms of 2mm-thick sheets. High-purity (no less than 99.9%) aluminum, copper and tin were melted to obtain alloy melt with nominal compositions of 79% Al, 20% Sn, 1% Cu.

The steel sheets were machined to 150mm diameter plates. The plate surfaces were then ground and polished mechanically. A special flux composed mainly of K_2ZrF_6 was used to protect the steel plate from oxidation and absorption during pre-heating the specimen to the required temperature. Both the flux-coated specimen and the bonding die were preheated in a hot-press at where the liquid-solid pressure bonding was realized when the aluminum alloy melt was moved into the die from a melting furnace (the melting process followed metallurgy standards including degassing, deslagging, rabbling and teeming). The bonding pressure was maintained for 30 s, and then the consolidated couples were removed from the die and cooled in air. The bonding system is shown in Figure 1 and the major processing parameters are listed in Table 1.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the liquid-solid pressure bonding system

The laminated samples were sectioned normal to the solid-liquid interfaces and then mechanically polished. The bimetallic samples were examined by scanning electron microscopy. Composition of the phases and the concentration profiles were obtained by electron microprobe. X-ray diffraction was used to identify the interface phases. The bonded samples were also machined to shear test specimens to examine the mechanical properties of the interfaces.

Table 1: Experimental conditions

Parameter	Value
Liquid alloy temperature(°C)	730~820
Steel sheet pre-heat temperature(°C)	120
Bonding Pressure(MPa)	0~60
Pressuring time (s)	30
Die pre-heat temperature(°C)	120
Concentration of flux solution(wt%)	5
Flux-coating time (s)	15

Figure 1. The specimen for shear strength test (mm)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Processing Parameters

The influence of the parameters was studied based on the shear strength values of the samples fabricated under above experimental conditions. The shear strength of the bonded samples is shown in Figure 2 and 3 as a function of liquid-phase temperature and bonding pressure, respectively. The optimum temperature for liquid-phase is 790 °C from the viewpoint of the bond strength and the bonding pressure has a favorable influence on bonding process, i.e., the higher the bonding pressure, the higher the interface shear strength. The effects of these processing parameters on bonding strength can be attributed to the different material behaviors and interface structures under different conditions.

Figure 2. Interface shear strength of the laminated materials vs the temperature of the liquid phase (bonding pressure 40 MPa)

Figure 3. Interface shear strength of the laminated materials vs. the bonding pressures (liquid phase temperature 790°C)

The fact that poor interface properties are obtained when the temperatures of liquid phase is relatively low, e.g., 730°C, can be attributed to the low intersolubility between Al and Sn elements that usually leads to a continuous layer of tin at interfaces. Although the diffusibility and intersolubility of relevant atoms can be enhanced with the increase of liquid phase temperature, another process, namely reaction process, is also promoted at higher temperatures (i.e., higher driving force for chemical reaction), degrading bonding properties greatly by introducing a large amount of intermetallic compounds to the interfaces. So the shear strength is poor (about 15MPa) when the temperature of liquid phase is 820°C. Based on the curve shown in Figure 2, it is suggested that an optimum balance between positive factors (intersolubility and diffusibility) and negative factors (interface segregation and reaction) is obtained when the temperature of the liquid phase is 790°C.

Bonding pressure improves interface properties greatly by accelerating the diffusion process and subsequently forming metallurgical bond at the interfaces. The heat-exchange between die system and liquid metal is also promoted under applied pressure, resulting in a high cooling rate and a high solidifying rate for the aluminum alloy. So the segregation of tin is restrained and the structures of the solidified aluminum alloys are homogenized.

Interface Structures

The ideal interface structure is a uniform and continuous diffusion layer with reasonable thickness and without extensive segregation and reactions as shown in Figure 4. It can be seen from this figure that there is an intermediate layer (gray) with thickness of about 8 μm between the aluminum alloy area (dark) and the steel area (bright). The profile of the element scan is not “flat” (i.e., composite-constant layer) across the interface, indicating limited intermetallic compounds. The sample with this interface structure demonstrated shear strength as high as 45 MPa.

A continuous layer of tin segregation was found at the interfaces for the samples fabricated under low temperature conditions. This phenomenon can be accounted for by the poor intersolubility of the liquid alloy at low temperatures. Figure 5 shows the microstructure of the interface with substantial tin segregation. This segregation layer appears bright in the figure and has a thickness of about 6 μm . With the presence of this continuous layer, the interface properties is thought to be seriously degraded because of the low strength of pure tin. The shear strength of this type of bonds is in the range of 14~22 MPa under current fabrication and test conditions.

The formation and growth of intermetallic compound layers at interfaces have been observed. Figure 6 shows a typical microstructure formed at 820°C. The electron microprobe analysis revealed that the phases present at the interface are Fe_2Al_5 and FeAl_3 . X-ray diffraction patterns also confirmed this observation. Figure 7 gives us a direct evidence of the presence of compounds. The profiles of element analysis (Fe and Al) showing plats (depicted by the arrows) at the interface indicate a constant composition in this area, i.e., a layer of Fe-Al compounds. The FeAl_3 phase is dispersed in the solidified aluminum alloy while the Fe_2Al_5 appears highly irregular with peaks and valleys. This tongue-like interface was also observed in other investigation [4-5]. The brittleness of the intermetallic compounds and the irregularity of the interface morphology have great effects on the mechanical properties of the couple. The samples having interface structures similar to Figure 6 showed shear strength of about 20 MPa.

The addition of 1 wt% rare-earth element to the aluminum alloy has great influences on the bonding process and it is interesting to note that no observable intermediate layer is present at the interface (see Figure 8). But it is difficult to conclude that rare-earth elements can resist the diffusion and reaction processes because of the shortage of the knowledge on the behavior of rare-earth elements during diffusion bonding. The fact that all the samples with rare-earth additions (subsequently without evident bonding layer) showed relatively low shear strength (20~25 MPa) revealed the importance of the continuous and uniform intermediate layer for the bonded couple. Rare-earth elements also have effects on the liquid structure: the distribution of tin in the solidified aluminum alloy was homogenized and no large-scale segregation occurred during solidification.

Figure 4. The microstructure of the interface with continuous and uniform morphology (Superimposed with element analysis)

Figure 5. The microstructure of the interface with a layer of tin segregation

Figure 6. The microstructure of the interface with extensive chemical reaction products

Figure 7. The element analysis across the intermetallic compounds at interface

Figure 8. The microstructure of the interface without evident intermediate layer (superimposed with element analysis)

CONCLUSIONS

1. Fundamental research on solid-liquid pressure bonding technology have been carried out using steel/Al20Sn1Cu system, confirming the technical potential of a novel route combining rolling and casting processes for laminated composites fabrication.
2. The bond properties are related to processing parameters such as bonding pressure and thermal conditions. The former has a positive effect on bonding process and can be selected based on equipment conditions, while the later must be determined with respect to material behaviors such as segregation, reaction and diffusion. For this bonding system, the optimal processing temperature of aluminum alloy is 790 °C.
3. Shear strength as high as 43 MPa can be obtained for steel/aluminum alloy laminated composites fabricated through solid-liquid pressure bonding under liquid phase temperature 790°C and boding pressure 40MPa.
4. Interface investigation revealed two kinds of interface defects, tin segregation and intermetallic compounds. Each of them can lead to considerable reduction in interface shear strength. Tin segregation was found to occur at low processing temperatures, while the intermetallic compounds were formed at high processing temperatures.

5. The addition of rare-earth elements to liquid alloy resulted in a narrow interface without evident intermediate layer, and subsequently decreased the bond strength. But the distribution of tin in the solidified aluminum alloys was homogenized in this case.

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